

Reconstruction Using Pedicled Inguinal Flap Type Mc Gregor in the Right Hand First Digit, Secondary to Necrosis Due to Loxosceles Spider Bite: Case Report

Villarreal-Aguirre Patricio¹, Cisneros-Rodríguez Gilberto², Gonzalez-Ramirez Juan M.¹, Ovalle-Amaya Andrea¹, Granado-Flores Alexis A.¹

¹Department of General Surgery, Monclova General Hospital, Monclova, Coahuila, Mexico.

²Department of General Surgery, High Specialty Medical Unit Number 25 (UMAE 25), National Medical Center of the Northeast, Mexican Institute Of Social Security (IMSS), Monterrey, Nuevo León, México.

ABSTRACT

Loxosceles spider bite represents a relevant health problem in endemic regions, mainly due to its cutaneous manifestations characterized by progressive necrosis that is difficult to manage. We present the case of a 13-year-old female patient who arrived at our center with necrosis of the volar pulp of the right thumb, secondary to Loxosceles spider bite, showing rapid progression to ischemia and necrotic eschar despite initial management with specific antivenom, antihistamines, corticosteroids, and antibiotic therapy. In the absence of dermal matrices or other microsurgical resources, it was decided to perform reconstruction using a pedicled inguinal flap type McGregor, a classical technique described by McGregor and Morgan in 1972, based on the vascular axis of the superficial circumflex iliac artery. Surgical lavage, debridement of devitalized tissue, and subsequent rotation of the flap were performed, ensuring proper defect coverage and fixation. The postoperative course was uneventful, with flap division at 21 days and favorable clinical follow-up, preserving both function and aesthetic appearance of the thumb. This case highlights the validity and usefulness of the McGregor flap as a reconstructive alternative in complex hand injuries, even in less conventional etiologies such as cutaneous loxoscelism, underscoring its applicability in resource-limited settings. The evidence obtained reinforces the need to consider classical reconstructive techniques as part of the current surgical arsenal, while also promoting systematic documentation of these cases to enrich the existing literature.

KEYWORDS: McGregor Inguinal Flap, spider bite, Loxosceles, hand reconstruction, cutaneous necrosis, case report.

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INTRODUCTION

The Loxosceles spider ("Violin Spider") encompasses a group of 18 species within that genus, with an incidence still uncertain due to underreporting and lack of case registry. However, it is estimated that between 3,000 to 5,000 cases occur annually, with males being more frequently affected (>50% of cases), across a highly variable age range(3,8).

Its main complications are divided into two categories: systemic and cutaneous. We focus on the cutaneous form, which, unlike systemic involvement, presents zero mortality yet entails major aesthetic and functional consequences. Edema, ulceration, and necrosis are the primary cutaneous

effects, derived from the spider's venom mechanism, which is rich in phospholipases-D, metalloproteases, and cystine knot inhibitor peptides. Specifically, sphingomyelinase D is identified as the main necrosis-inducing factor, causing disruption of cell membranes and activation of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as IL-6 and TNF- α , leading to progressive tissue damage(11).

Ideally, management should occur within the first hours following the bite, including administration of specific antivenom (Reclusmyn), subsequent wound lavage, and vigilant monitoring to determine further intervention according to lesion evolution(3).

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Regarding reconstructive surgical management, the inguinal flap type McGregor represents a historically reliable option. Since its original description in 1972 by McGregor and Morgan, it has been based on the vascular axis of the superficial circumflex iliac artery, allowing robust axial coverage with low risk of necrosis and without requiring microsurgical techniques(1,7). Its classic indications include defects secondary to trauma, burns, or oncologic resections in the hand and forearm(5,9). However, its use in cutaneous loxoscelism lesions has been scarcely reported, becoming a clinically relevant area due to the frequency of such injuries in our setting and the need for accessible reconstructive options.

This case report describes the utilization of the McGregor inguinal flap in a pediatric patient with digital necrosis secondary to *Loxosceles* spider bite, providing practical information regarding its application in this context and contributing to the available evidence for future publications and protocols in hand reconstructive surgery.

CASE REPORT

A 13-year-old female patient, with no allergies, no chronic-degenerative conditions, and no relevant medical history. The patient was apparently bitten on May 6th, 2025, in the late afternoon-evening. She presented at our hospital on May 7th in the morning, reporting intense pain at the bite site, as well as ischemia in the digital tip, hematoma, and a small necrotic eschar (Figure 1).

FIGURE 1. Hematoma, ischemia, and necrotic eschar in the volar portion of the right thumb.

Specific antivenom was administered, along with corticosteroids, antihistamines, analgesics, antithrombotic agents, and antibiotic therapy (Hydrocortisone, Diphenhydramine, Enoxaparin, Clindamycin, and Dicloxacillin). The wound was monitored, and dressings, hematoma drainage, and debridement were indicated. Over the following days, there was significant improvement in pain and edema, and the necrotic eschar became clearly delimited (Figure 2). On May 12th, 2025, surgical debridement in three stages was performed (Figure 3).

FIGURE 2. Necrotic eschar on the fingertip, with surrounding devitalized tissue

FIGURE 3. Devitalized tissue and pulp involvement.

A new necrotic eschar subsequently formed, which was resected, and wound care and monitoring continued. At this point, there was no neurovascular compromise in the finger. Given the absence of infectious signs and clinical improvement (Figure 4), surgical intervention with a McGregor Inguinal Flap was scheduled and performed on May 15th, 2025.

FIGURE 4. Decrease in edema

Following full surgical protocol and a successful time-out with combined anesthesia (neuraxial block and sedation), asepsis and antisepsis were conducted, sterile fields were placed, and the surgical area was marked with tincture (Figure 5). Anatomical structures were identified, skin was incised

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with a cold scalpel, dissection was carried out using monopolar energy, and the superficial circumflex iliac artery and its corresponding vein were located. The flap was subsequently freed (Figures 6), rotated, and after surgical lavage and debridement of the affected first digit (Figure 7), it was sutured to the defect using 4-0 and 5-0 Nylon sutures (Figure 8). The donor site was closed with 3-0 Monocryl. The arm and forearm were fixed to the patient's skin using 2-0 Nylon sutures. The procedure was completed with sterile dressing coverage.

Figure 8. Thumb attached to inguinal flap.

The postoperative period was uneventful, with good clinical evolution. The patient was discharged on May 16th, 2025, with antibiotic to complete a 10-day course. Follow-up visits were scheduled for 7 and 14 days postoperatively, both without complications. Flap division was scheduled for June 5th, 2025, and was carried out without incident (Figures 9 and 10).

FIGURE 5. Surgical marking of the inguinal flap area and Flap dissection in progress.

FIGURE 6. Flap liberated.

Figure 9. Donor site wound post-flap liberation.

Figure 7. Debrided affected thumb, prior to flap attachment.

The patient was seen 7 days after flap division to evaluate sutures, which were removed on day 10 post-division, again without complications (Figure 11).

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Figure 10. Released thumb post-flap, anterior and lateral view.

Figure 11. Thumb 10 days post-flap release, sutures removed and anterior view.

DISCUSSION

Since its original description by McGregor and Morgan in 1973, the inguinal flap has been widely used in hand reconstructive surgery. Its main advantage lies in its reliable axial anatomy, low risk of necrosis, and the ability to avoid microsurgery, which is especially valuable in settings with limited resources or where more sophisticated perforator flaps are unavailable(1,7).

In the literature, the use of the inguinal flap has been well documented in scenarios such as extensive burns, traumatic defects, and post-oncologic reconstruction. Niño de Guzmán et al. reported a 96% success rate in hand trauma coverage using the McGregor flap, with a complication rate below 10%, data that correlate with our experience in this case (5,9). However, its application in cutaneous loxoscelism lesions has

been scarcely reported. This is relevant because tissue necrosis secondary to *Loxosceles* spider bite can produce complex, deep, and poorly defined defects, challenging conventional reconstructive techniques(1,6,7). Sphingomyelinase D, the principal implicated toxin, triggers a prolonged inflammatory process that complicates precise delimitation of viable tissue borders, making continuous monitoring and sequential surgical intervention indispensable (11).

In this case, the McGregor flap was chosen due to its vascular reliability, appropriate size, and relative technical ease. The decision was supported by good clinical evolution, with no signs of neurovascular compromise, and by the fact that other reconstructive options (such as dermal matrices or composite grafts) were not available. This choice aligns with the recommendation of García and Sánchez, who highlight the usefulness of the flap in anatomically complex areas with high functional demand such as the hand(2).

Furthermore, early surgical management in this type of necrosis is crucial, as described by Romero and López, who emphasize that the local evolution of the loxoscelic lesion can be unpredictable, requiring continuous assessment and timely interventions(11). The sequential approach of eschar excision, wound care, and then definitive coverage allowed optimization of the recipient bed, thereby reducing the risk of complications. It is important to note that despite its benefits, the inguinal flap presents limitations such as the need for prolonged immobilization and a visible scar at the donor site. Bernal Ornelas et al. note that although these scars are generally well tolerated, they must be considered as part of the informed consent process with the patient(1).

In pediatric patients, its relatively thin skin thickness and tissue elasticity offer aesthetic and functional advantages at the recipient site. Sánchez and González recommend a careful immobilization protocol to avoid joint contractures or stiffness in this age group(12). Finally, this case contributes to the literature by demonstrating that even outside its traditional indications, the McGregor flap can be an effective tool in complex lesions caused by unusual etiologies such as spider bite. While further case reports and clinical series are needed to consolidate this indication, the experience shared here provides initial evidence to consider it in similar contexts.

CONCLUSION

The pedicled inguinal flap type McGregor has proven to be a versatile, reliable, and accessible tool for the reconstruction of complex hand defects, particularly in the first digit, where pinch function is vital. In the presented case, its use preserved not only the length and volume of the thumb but also its mobility, without the need for advanced microsurgical techniques.

This report emphasizes the importance of considering classical techniques such as the McGregor flap in settings

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where resources are limited or where more modern alternatives are not available. Its consistent vascularization, ease of design, and technical safety make it a current and viable option, especially in pediatric patients, where long-term functional and aesthetic prognosis is critical.

The existing literature indicates success rates above 90% with the McGregor flap in hand and forearm reconstruction, and although its specific application in necrosis due to loxoscelism is limited, the results observed in this case support its indication. We recommend considering this approach for replication in similar contexts, while also promoting the reporting of more cases to enrich the evidence regarding its application in injuries caused by unusual etiologies such as cutaneous loxoscelism.

Early evaluation accompanied by a strategic reconstructive plan can significantly change the functional prognosis of these patients. The integration of multicenter protocols and national registries on the use of the inguinal flap in this context would be of great value to the surgical community.

*Patient consent was obtained for the use of images.

*No conflicts of interest declared.

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